

Studies in Copper(II) Complexes: Part V. Glycinato- (α , α' -Dipyridyl)Copper(II) and Related Complexes

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A number of mixed chelates of copper (II) containing glycine or α -(DL)-alanine and α , α' -dipyridyl, o-phenanthroline or 5-nitro-o-phenanthroline has been synthesized and characterised. These are of the type, $[\text{Cu}(\text{AA})(\text{XY})\text{Z} \cdot \text{X} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$ (where AA = α , α' -dipyridyl, o-phenanthroline or 5-nitro-o-phenanthroline, XYH = glycine or α -(DL)-alanine and Z = chloride, bromide and iodide). These are royal blue to blue in colour, crystalline, provide uni-univalent electrolyte conductance and show usual magnetic moments 1.8–1.9 B.M. Their solution absorption spectra in water, methanol, ethyleneglycol and dimethylsulfoxide have been recorded. Absorption bands around 15,400–17,000 cm^{-1} and some slight shifting of these spectral bands on changing the solvents indicate distorted octahedral structure.

Earlier in this series^{1,2} studies on copper(II) hetero complexes containing biguanides or substituted biguanide and the heterocyclic bidentate, such as α , α' -dipyridyl, o-phenanthroline, 5-nitro-o-phenanthroline have appeared. The formation constant values of some of these mixed chelate systems were of reasonably high order. Formation constants of some mixed ligand chelates containing α , α' -dipyridyl and one of pyrocatechol, tiron, salicylic acid etc. have been reported and these values are also of a high order.³ It is known that α , α' -dipyridyl forms 1:1 chelate with copper(II) which is green between pH 3 and 4, and changes to blue on raising the pH. At this stage hydroxo-complex, a di- μ -hydroxo-bis [α , α' -dipyridyl copper (II)] is formed. This compound does not disproportionate readily to the metal hydroxide and a chelate compound containing 1:2 metal complex, indicating the reasonable stability of the mono-complex in solution.³ We have, therefore, undertaken this present study of the action of glycine or α -(DL)-alanine on the above copper (II) hydroxo-complexes of the heterocyclic ligands.

Action of glycine or α -alanine on di- μ -hydroxo-bis [α , α' -dipyridyl copper (II)] around pH 7.5 leads to the formation of a deep blue to royal blue colour. On proper concentration of the resulting solution, the mixed complexes, glycinato(α , α' -dipyridyl) copper (II) or α -(DL)-alaninato (α , α' -dipyridyl)copper(II) can be isolated in the form of chloride, bromide or iodide salts. Similar results are also obtained with o-phenanthroline and 5-nitro-o-phenanthroline. The complexes in general are crystalline and are highly soluble in water. Their aqueous solutions provide usual conductance values 96–100 mhos $\text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$ for uni-univalent electrolytes⁴. They also provide usual paramagnetic values 1.8–1.9 B.M. (cf. Table—II).

The absorption spectra of the complexes have been run in water, methanol, dimethylsulfoxide and ethyleneglycol. In general, the complexes show absorption bands around

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3. G. A. L'Heureux and A. E. Martell, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 481.
4. M. M. Jones, "Elementary Coordination Chemistry," Prentice-Hall, Inc., 1964, p. 254.

Fig. 1. Solution Absorption Spectra of a Mixed Complex in Different Solvents. [Cu (dipy) (gly)] Cl. 1.5 H₂O., 0.004M in ethyleneglycol (curve 1), in water (curve 2), in dimethylsulfoxide (curve 3) and in methanol (curve 4).

TABLE I

Electronic Spectral Data of the Mixed Chelates

Complex	Medium	Absorption Spectral Band in cm ⁻¹	ϵ_{max} .
1. [Cu (dipy) (gly)] Cl. 1.5 H ₂ O	Water	16,950—15,870	50.0
	MeOH	16,390—16,130	58.5
	DMSO	16,130—15,380	67.0
	Etglycol	16,950—16,130	51.3
2. [Cu (dipy) (gly)] I. H ₂ O	Water	16,670—15,870	51.5
	MeOH	16,950—16,390	*
3. [Cu (dipy) (α -alan)] Cl. 1.5 H ₂ O	Water	16,950—15,870	51.0
	MeOH	16,390—16,130	56.2
	DMSO	16,130—15,380	69.0
	Etglycol	16,950—16,130	52.5
4. [Cu(dipy) (α -alan)] I. H ₂ O	Water	16,950—15,870	53.5
	MeOH	16,670—16,130	66.5
5. [Cu (o-phen) (gly)] Cl. 3H ₂ O	Water	16,670—15,620	51.0
6. [Cu (o-phen) (gly)] I. H ₂ O	Water	16,390—15,870	56.5
	MeOH	16,130—15,870	*
7. [Cu (o-phen) (α -alan)] Cl. 1.5 H ₂ O	Water	16,950 15,870	58.8
8. [Cu (o-phen) (α -alan)] I. 2H ₂ O	Water	16,390—15,870	64.0
	MeOH	16,390—15,870	*
9. [Cu (nitrophen) (gly)] Cl. 0.5 H ₂ O	Water	16,670—15,620	50.0
10. [Cu (nitrophen) (gly)] I. H ₂ O	Water	16,670—15,620	50.0
	MeOH	16,670—15,870	60.0

*The optical densities were measured in saturated solutions. Due to some uncertainty in the total solubility of the complex, the molar extinction co-efficients are rather of poor accuracy and have hence been omitted.

DMSO = Dimethylsulfoxide, Etglycol = ethyleneglycol, dipy = α , α' -dipyridyl, o-phen = O-phenanthroline, nitrophen = 5-nitro-o-phenanthroline glyH = Glycine, and α -alanH = α -(DL)-alanine.

15,400—17,000 cm^{-1} , with some slight variation depending on the solvents. These shifts do not follow a uniform pattern for all the complexes, but some slight variation on changing the solvents is observed. (cf. Table—I and Fig.—1). These variations together with the location of absorption bands at not very high frequency (say, around 20,000 cm^{-1}) possibly suggest tetragonally distorted octahedral structure⁵ for the complexes.

EXPERIMENTAL

(1) *Glycinato*(α , α' -dipyridyl) *Copper(II) Chloride*: To an aqueous solution of copper (II) chloride (0.17 g in 2 ml.) an alcoholic solution of α , α' -dipyridyl (0.15 g in 2 ml.) was added with stirring. A green crystalline precipitate was formed slowly. The pH of the mixture was raised to 7.5—8 by dil. (2N) NH_4OH when the green precipitate turns light blue. This light blue precipitate was then treated with an aqueous solution of glycine (pH 7.5—8; 0.08 g in 2 ml.) with stirring. The precipitate disappeared slowly forming a deep blue solution. This solution was then concentrated to ~ 2 ml. on a steam bath and allowed to stand (at pH 7.5—8) at room temperature overnight. A deep blue crystalline precipitate formed, which was recrystallised from little warm water (pH 7.5—8) and finally washed with alcohol, when the deep blue colour of the precipitate faded away to a light one, which however is restored on drying in air. During recrystallisation, sometimes, few green crystals appear as impurities due to the lowering of pH below or at 7. These green crystals were removed by leaching with alcohol.

(2) *Glycinato* (α , α' -dipyridyl) *Copper(II) Bromide*: The pure *glycinato* (α , α' -dipyridyl) copper(II) chloride was dissolved in 1-2 ml. of water (pH 7.5—8) and was treated with an aqueous solution of KBr. The solution was concentrated to a small volume and cooled. The bright blue crystals were filtered, dried in air. The dried crude crystals were dissolved in ~ 2 ml. of warm water (pH 7.5—8), cooled at room temperature for 2—3 hrs, when bright deep blue crystals separated out.

(3) *Glycinato* (α , α' -dipyridyl) *copper(II) Iodide*: The pure *glycinato*(α , α' -dipyridyl) copper (II) chloride salt was dissolved in ~ 2 ml. of water and was treated with a dil. solution of KI when dark blue crystals along with some yellow ones formed on allowing it to stand overnight. The crystals were dissolved in warm water, filtered rapidly when a blackish residue left undissolved. The clear blue filtrate was cooled in ice when a royal blue crystalline mass, soluble in ethanol and methanol was obtained.

The following α -(DL)alaninato (α , α' -dipyridyl)copper(II) complexes, *glycinato* / α -(DL)-alaninato(o-phenanthroline)Copper(II) complexes and *glycinato* / α -(DL) alaninato(5-nitro-o-phenanthroline)copper(II) complexes were prepared by procedures similar to those of the corresponding *glycinato*(α , α' -dipyridyl)Copper(II) complexes. The elemental analyses of the complexes are given in table II.

It was generally experienced in the above syntheses that while recrystallising, the mixed chelate crystals were often contaminated with little shining green coloured complex presumably a di- μ -hydroxo-bis [o-phenanthroline/ α , α' -dipyridyl copper (II)] salt or a bis(o-phenanthroline/ α , α' -dipyridyl) copper(II). However, addition of a drop or two of

5. M. Goodgame and L. I. B. Haines, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, (A), 175.

6. P. W. Selwood "Magnetochemistry," Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, 1956, p. 78.

dil. NH_4OH , raising the pH thereby, obviated the appearance of the green crystals. In some case, washing with a little alcohol also removed the green crystals.

TABLE II

Elemental Analyses, Conductances and Magnetic moments

Complex	Colour	Analysis				% H_2O	Λ_M in aq. soln (mhos $\text{cm}^2\text{mole}^{-1}$) at 24°C	μ_{eff} B.M. (at T° abs.)
		% Cu	% N	% Cl/Br/I	% H_2O			
1. [Cu(dipy) (gly)] Cl. 1.5 H_2O	Deep blue	Found : 17.78 Reqd. : 17.83	11.70 11.76	9.85 9.92	7.60 7.58	97.11	1.92 (299)*	
2. [Cu (dipy) (gly)] Br. H_2O	Bright blue	Found : 16.10 Reqd. : 16.19	10.60 10.68	20.38 20.35	4.43 4.50			
3. [Cu (dipy) (gly)] I. H_2O	Royal blue	Found : 14.40 Reqd. : 14.47	9.49 9.49	28.80 28.86	4.21 4.10	98.20	1.94(297)	
4. [Cu(dipy) α -alan] Cl. 1.5 H_2O	Deep blue	Found : 17.10 Reqd. : 17.16	11.40 11.35	9.63 9.59	7.34 7.29			
5. [Cu(dipy) (α -alan)] Br. 2 H_2O	Deep blue	Found : 14.95 Reqd. : 15.01	9.88 9.91	18.82 18.88	8.02 8.40	100.10	1.83 (302)	
6. [Cu (dipy) (α -alan)] I. H_2O	Sky blue	Found : 13.98 Reqd. : 14.05	9.20 9.28	28.00 28.06	3.87 3.97			
7. [Cu(o-phen) (gly)] Cl. 3 H_2O	Deep blue	Found : 15.49 Reqd. : 15.56	10.38 10.29	8.65 8.70	13.30 13.23	96.27	1.80(298)	
8. [Cu (o-phen) (gly)] Br. 2 H_2O	Bright blue	Found : 14.58 Reqd. : 14.62	9.52 9.60	18.24 18.30	8.09 8.20			
9. [Cu (o-phen) (gly)] I. 2 H_2O	Blue	Found : 13.12 Reqd. : 13.23	8.68 8.72	26.40 26.43	7.34 7.48	101.50	1.84(298)	
10. [Cu (o-phen) (α -alan)] Cl. 1.5 H_2O	Deep blue	Found : 16.08 Reqd. : 16.13	10.58 10.65	9.18 9.05	6.71 6.57			
11. [Cu (o-phen) (α -alan)] Br. 2 H_2O	Deep blue	Found : 14.12 Reqd. : 14.20	9.44 9.38	17.92 17.87	7.91 8.03	101.50	1.84(298)	
12. [Cu (o-phen) (α -alan)] I. 2 H_2O	Sky blue	Found : 12.80 Reqd. : 12.85	8.41 8.49	25.60 25.68	7.29 7.27			
13. [Cu(nitrophen) (gly)] Cl. 0.5 H_2O	Greenish blue	Found : 15.60 Reqd. : 15.62	13.74 13.75	8.65 8.72	2.30 2.21	101.50	1.84(298)	
14. [Cu(nitrophen) (gly)] Br.	Light bluish green	Found : 14.31 Reqd. : 14.36	12.59 12.65	18.11 18.01				
15. [Cu(nitrophen) (gly)] I. H_2O	Olive green	Found : 12.48 Reqd. : 12.51	11.10 11.04	25.06 25.02	3.00 3.54			

*Figures in parentheses indicate the temps. at which measurements were made.

μ_{eff} was calculated from the relation $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.84 (\chi_M(\text{corr.}) \times T)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ B.M. (where T = Absolute temperature).

Λ_M (molar conductance) = $1 \times \text{mean} \lambda \alpha$, (where $\lambda \alpha = \lambda_v(1 + 0.692 \times n_1 \times n_2 \times v^{-\frac{1}{2}})$ and n_1 and n_2 are the valencies of the ions.)

In general, the α -alaninato-(5-nitro-o-phenanthroline) copper(II) mixed chelates were far more soluble so that isolation of the complexes did not appear practicable.

General Properties : All the complexes are crystalline, and are soluble commonly in water, dimethylsulfoxide, ethyleneglycol, methanol and insoluble in benzene, acetone, chloroform etc.

Analytical Methods : Water of hydration was determined by loss at 110°C for one hour.

Nitrogen was estimated by combustion technique.

Halogens were estimated as silver halides by the usual methods.

Copper was first precipitated as CuS with H₂S. This precipitate was then dissolved in nitric acid—sulphuric acid mixture and was estimated iodometrically. In some cases copper was also estimated by KHSO₄—fusion technique.

Magnetic susceptibility measurements of the complexes at room temperature were made by a Gouy Balance with field strength 8.366×10^3 gauss using G.R. grade copper (II) sulphate pentahydrate as a standard. Diamagnetic corrections were taken from Selwood.⁶

Conductivities were measured by Philips conductivity bridge type PR 9500.

The absorption spectra of the complexes in water, methanol, dimethylsulfoxide, and ethyleneglycol were measured at 4×10^{-3} M concentration in a Hilger and Watts UVIspek Spectrophotometer over the range of 370—1000 m μ , using glass cells with 1 cm light path.

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